

Heterogeneous effects of fibroblast-myocyte coupling in different regions of the human atria under conditions of atrial fibrillation

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10 **Abstract**

11 Background: Atrial fibrillation (AF), the most common cardiac arrhythmia, is characterized by
12 alteration of the action potential (AP) propagation. Under persistent AF, myocytes undergo
13 electrophysiological and structural remodeling, which involves fibroblast proliferation and
14 differentiation, modifying the substrate for AP propagation. The aim of this study was to analyze the
15 effects on the AP of fibroblast-myocyte coupling during AF and its propagation in different regions of
16 the atria.

17 Methods: Isolated myocytes were coupled to different numbers of fibroblasts using the established AP
18 models and tissue simulations were performed by randomly distributing fibroblasts. Fibroblast
19 formulations were updated to match recent experimental data. Major ion current conductances of the
20 myocyte model were modified to simulate AP heterogeneity in four different atrial regions (right atrium
21 posterior wall, crista terminalis, left atrium posterior wall, and pulmonary vein) according to
22 experimental and computational studies.

23 Results: The results of the coupled myocyte-fibroblast simulations suggest that a more depolarized
24 membrane potential and higher fibroblast membrane capacitance have a greater impact on action
25 potential duration and myocyte maximum depolarization velocity. The number of coupled fibroblasts
26 and the stimulation frequency are determining factors in altering myocyte AP. Strand simulations show
27 that conduction velocity tends to homogenize in all regions, while the left atrium is more likely to be
28 affected by fibroblast and AP propagation block is more likely to occur. The pulmonary vein is the
29 most affected region, even at low fibroblast densities. In 2D sheets with randomly placed fibroblasts,
30 wavebreaks are observed in the low density (10%) central fibrotic zone and when fibroblast density
31 increases (40%) propagation in the fibrotic region is practically blocked. At densities of 10% and 20%
32 the width of the vulnerable window increases with respect to control but is decreased at 40%.

33 Conclusions: Myocyte-fibroblast coupling characteristics heterogeneously affect AP propagation and
34 features in the different atrial zones, and myocytes from the left atria are more sensitive to fibroblast
35 coupling.

36 **1 Introduction**

37 Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most common cardiac arrhythmia and is becoming more prevalent with
38 population ageing (Iwasaki et al., 2011). In persistent atrial fibrillation (PeAF), lasting longer than 7
39 days (Kirchhof et al., 2016), spontaneous, pharmacological, or ablative resumption of sinus rhythm is
40 infrequent with prompt recurrences or commonly failed cardioversions (Jalife and Kaur, 2015).

41 In PeAF, cardiac tissue experiences structural and electrical remodeling driven by changes of the
42 extracellular matrix, fibroblast differentiation, fatty and inflammatory infiltration, and ion channel
43 remodeling, among other alterations (Kirchhof et al., 2016). The heterogeneities in the atrial substrate
44 cause fiber discontinuities and local conduction disturbances favoring re-entries (Nattel and Dobrev,
45 2017).

46 The atria have a complex anatomical structure, differences between the right and left atrium, and
47 complex structures like the pulmonary vein or left and right appendages (Ferrer et al., 2015; Sanchez-
48 Quintana et al., 2012). They all have their own electrophysiological characteristics, which determine
49 specific action potential (AP) waveforms and conduction velocities (CV), which are crucial to AF
50 pathophysiology.

51 Approximately 75% of the adult myocardium tissue volume is occupied by myocytes, accounting for
52 only 30-40% of the total number of cells (Biernacka and Frangogiannis, 2011). Fibroblasts are
53 considered as the predominant non-myocyte cell. They become active under inflammatory response
54 and then differentiate into myofibroblasts (Chacar et al., 2017) by different pathways (e.g. oxidative
55 stress, atrial dilatation, calcium overload, inflammation), although the precise mechanisms have not
56 yet been established (Jalife and Kaur, 2015). Myofibroblasts differ from fibroblasts in that they develop
57 contractile proteins and exhibit a more depolarized resting membrane potential (Salvarani et al., 2017)
58 and greater membrane capacitance (Sridhar et al., 2017). The differences in resting membrane potential
59 and membrane capacitance between fibroblasts and myofibroblasts might have an important
60 repercussion on the electrophysiology of coupled myocytes.

61 Recent experimental studies have shown that fibroblasts express voltage-dependent sodium channels
62 allowing an inward current (I_{Na}) (Chatelier et al., 2012; Koivumäki et al., 2014a; Poulet et al., 2016).
63 Although they are not electrically excitable they may affect the myocytes' electrophysiological
64 properties (Gaudesius et al., 2003; Kohl et al., 2005; Miragoli et al., 2006). Several animal experimental
65 models have shown that fibroblasts electrically couple to myocytes and alter their AP (Burstein et al.,
66 2007; Gaudesius et al., 2003; Jalife and Kaur, 2015; Jousset et al., 2016; Quinn et al., 2016; Rohr,
67 2011; Rook et al., 1992). Kohl et al. (1994) found that fibroblasts reacted electrically with myocytes
68 through gap junctions and this was later corroborated in vitro in several animal species (Camelliti et
69 al., 2004; Gaudesius et al., 2003; Kohl et al., 2005). However, the extent of (in vivo) fibroblast–
70 myocyte electrotonic coupling in native myocardium remains controversial (Kohl and Gourdie, 2014).
71 Recently, a study by Quinn et al. (2016) showed the existence of tunneling nanotube connections
72 between excitable and non-excitable cells (e.g. myofibroblasts) in cardiac scar border tissue at the
73 border zone of the scar in mice hearts. Similarly, Burstein et al. (2007) observed fibroblasts
74 proliferation and differentiation into myofibroblasts during atrial fibrillation in in vivo canine hearts.
75 Fibroblast proliferation has also been observed in human hearts (Fukumoto et al., 2016; Krul et al.,
76 2015), in regions with altered conduction velocity, although electrical coupling has not been
77 demonstrated.

78 Computational simulations of the cellular electrophysiology have become a powerful tool for studying
79 the role that fibroblasts play in the atrial substrate (Koivumäki et al., 2014a; MacCannell et al., 2007;
80 Maleckar et al., 2009). Their flexibility permits modifying the cellular electrophysiology and varying
81 different characteristics to analyze the impact of electrotonic coupling with electrically remodeled
82 myocytes in PeAF (McDowell et al., 2013; Morgan et al., 2014; Sridhar et al., 2017). MacCannell et
83 al. (2007) formulated an active and a passive model for fibroblasts electrophysiology, considering a
84 capacitance and an ohmic resistance in the first case and a capacitance and four ionic currents in the
85 second case. The active model is more realistic and has a major impact on myocytes, this is why in the
86 present study the active model is implemented. Simulations also offer the possibility of studying how
87 fibroblasts can change arrhythmia dynamics by reducing CV and introducing heterogeneities in the
88 atrial substrate (Saha et al., 2018; Tanaka et al., 2007).

89 The present simulation study analyzes the effects of fibroblast-myocyte coupling in PeAF in specific
90 structurally and electrophysiologically remodeled atrial tissues and compares the effect of fibroblasts
91 and myofibroblasts on myocyte AP features, tissue conduction velocity and vulnerability to re-entries.

92 **2 Material and Methods**

93 **2.1 Myocyte electrophysiological models**

94 The human atrial AP model proposed by Koivumaki et al. (2011) was used to simulate atrial APs. To
95 reproduce the tissue electrophysiology of different anatomical atrial regions, we modified the
96 conductance of five ionic currents: transient outward K^+ current (I_{to}), potassium rapid current (I_{Kr}),
97 potassium slow current (I_{Ks}), time independent K^+ current (I_{K1}), and L-type Ca^{2+} current (I_{CaL}) as
98 proposed in previous simulation studies (Ferrer et al., 2015; Krueger et al., 2012). The conductance
99 values, shown in Table 1, were modified according to the experimental values to reproduce the AP
100 waveform in all four regions: right atrium posterior wall (RA), crista terminalis (CT), left atrium
101 posterior wall (LA), and the pulmonary vein (PV) areas.

102 **2.2 Ionic remodeling**

103 Table 2 shows the values used to introduce AF electrical remodeling in all atrial regions by modifying
104 ion channel conductances for I_{CaL} , I_{to} , I_{K1} , sustained outward K^+ current (I_{sus}), Na^+/Ca^{2+} exchanger
105 (NCX), sarcoplasmic reticulum Ca^{2+} ATPase (SERCA) pump, and ryanodine receptors (RyR), and
106 specific calcium handling parameters, such as phospholamban (PLB), sarcolipin (SLN), and the
107 baseline phosphorylation (phos). Dilation was also modeled by increasing the length of the cell by a
108 factor of 1.1 (see Table 2) as described in Koivumaki et al. (2014b).

109 **2.3 Fibroblast electrophysiological model**

110 Fibroblast electrophysiology was represented according to the Koivumaki et al. (2014a) model.
111 Membrane sodium current was updated to match recent experimental results (Poulet et al., 2016) (see
112 Table S1). The uncoupled fibroblast resting membrane potential (RMP_f) was set to -45 mV or -26 mV,
113 as suggested by experimental data (Poulet et al., 2016; Salvarani et al., 2017). These values were
114 obtained by shifting the gating variable for the time dependent potassium current as in previous
115 simulation studies (Maleckar et al., 2009; Morgan et al., 2016), and shown in Table S2. The fibroblast
116 membrane capacitance (C_{mf}) values were varied within experimental ranges (6.3 pF and 50.4 pF)
117 (MacCannell et al., 2007; McArthur et al., 2015; Poulet et al., 2016; Sridhar et al., 2017; Xie et al.,
118 2009). Following previous experimental and simulation studies, we set RMP_f to -45 mV and C_{mf} to 6.3
119 pF for atrial fibroblasts (MacCannell et al., 2007; Maleckar et al., 2009), and a more depolarized RMP_f

120 of -26 mV and a C_{mf} of 50.4 pF for atrial myofibroblasts (Morgan et al., 2016; Poulet et al., 2016;
 121 Salvarani et al., 2017; Sridhar et al., 2017). The code is available and can be found at
 122 <http://hdl.handle.net/10251/120395>.

123 2.4 Cellular simulations (0D)

124 To compute the membrane potential in a cell, Equations (1, 2, 3) were used:

125

$$126 C_{myo} \frac{dV_{myo}}{dt} + I_{ion-my} + I_{gap} = 0 \quad (1)$$

127

$$128 C_{fib} \frac{dV_{fib}}{dt} + I_{ion-fib} - I_{gap} = 0 \quad (2)$$

129

$$130 I_{gap} = \sum_{i=0}^n G_{gap} (V_{myo} - V_{fib_i}) \quad (3)$$

131 where C_{myo} is the membrane capacitance of the myocyte, I_{ion-my} is the total ionic current flowing
 132 through ionic channels of the myocyte, V_{myo} is the membrane potential in the myocyte, C_{fib} is the
 133 membrane capacitance of the fibroblast, $I_{ion-fib}$ is the total ionic current flowing through ionic channels
 134 of the fibroblast, V_{fib} the membrane potential in the fibroblast, I_{gap} is the total ionic current flowing
 135 through the gap junction, n is the number of coupled fibroblasts to one myocyte and G_{gap} is the coupling
 136 conductance between myocyte and fibroblast. G_{gap} was set to 0.5 nS (Morgan et al., 2016), a value
 137 within the range of 0.3 - 8 nS measured in cultured myocyte-fibroblast experiments as used in previous
 138 simulation studies (MacCannell et al., 2007; Rook et al., 1992). The number of fibroblasts coupled to
 139 a single myocyte varied from 0 to 9 (Koivumäki et al., 2014a), as shown in Figure S1 in the
 140 supplementary material.

141 Stabilization of the cellular model of each region was achieved after 1000 stimuli of 2 ms duration and
 142 an amplitude of twice the threshold value. After this number of stimuli, APD₉₀ values and ion
 143 concentration ranges reached steady state. The basic cycle length (BCL) was 1 s, 250 ms, or 2 s.

144 The following features of the myocyte AP were measured: action potential duration at 90%
 145 repolarization (APD₉₀), depolarization upstroke velocity measured as the maximum variation of the
 146 depolarization phase (dV/dt_{max}), and the RMP.

147 2.5 Strand and tissue simulations

148 The diffusion-reaction equation (Eq. (4)) of the monodomain formalism was used to simulate AP
 149 electrical propagation:

150

$$151 \nabla \cdot (D \nabla V) = C_m \frac{dV}{dt} + I_{ion} \quad (4)$$

152 where D is the diffusion tensor, C_m is the membrane capacitance, and I_{ion} stands for ionic currents
 153 through the membrane. Diffusion coefficients were adjusted for the different atrial regions to achieve
 154 physiological conduction velocities (CVs) along a strand of myocytes in this particular tissue.

155 Diffusion coefficients for myocytes (D_m) were calculated and adjusted to achieve physiological CVs,
 156 yielding a D_m of 3.84 cm²/s in RA and LA (CV= 70 cm/s), a D_m of 6.384 cm²/s in CT (CV=100 cm/s),

157 and a D_m of $4.081 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ in PV ($CV=80 \text{ cm/s}$). In PeAF, the diffusion coefficient was reduced by 50%
 158 to reproduce gap junction remodeling (David M. Harrild, Craig S. Hen, 2000; Krogh-madsen et al.,
 159 2012; McDowell et al., 2012; Ten Tusscher et al., 2004).

160 For one-dimensional simulations (1D), a strand with a space discretization of $100 \mu\text{m}$ was used for
 161 myocytes (Courtemanche et al., 1998; Nygren et al., 1998; Sachse et al., 2008; Satoh et al., 1996) and
 162 $10 \mu\text{m}$ for fibroblasts-myofibroblasts (Brown et al., 2015; Sachse et al., 2008; Xie et al., 2009).
 163 Fibroblasts-myofibroblasts were randomly distributed along the strand at different densities (10%,
 164 20%, and 40%) using a uniform random probabilistic function. One hundred random distributions were
 165 generated for each density value (see Figure S3 in the supplemental material). The strand was paced
 166 with a BCL of 1 s for 50 s. The first element of the strand was stimulated with an amplitude of twice
 167 its threshold. CV was measured in the 50th pulse. The diffusion coefficient for elements with fibroblasts
 168 was halved with respect to the myocyte elements (Gomez et al., 2014b; Morgan et al., 2016; Vasquez
 169 et al., 2004).

170 Two-dimensional (2D) meshes representing cardiac tissues for RA and LA were built with a central
 171 fibrotic region of 2 cm diameter with different randomly distributed myofibroblast densities. Ten
 172 random distributions were implemented for each density (see Figures S1 and S3 in the supplemental
 173 material). The tissue grid had 524×524 elements with a spatial resolution of $100 \mu\text{m}$. An anisotropic
 174 ratio of 2.86:1 was considered in RA and LA (Ferrer et al., 2015).

175 To study the effect of myofibroblasts on vulnerability to reentry, reentrant activity was generated using
 176 cross-field stimulation protocol S1-S2. S1 stimuli consisted of 10 pulses applied to the left border of
 177 the computational mesh to stabilize the tissue and S2 was applied to the bottom left corner of the tissue.

178 In order to obtain the instantaneous location of the rotors, we used phase singularity (PS) detections
 179 (Gomez et al., 2014a; Gray et al., 1998; Martinez-Mateu et al., 2018; Sabir et al., 1974) first building
 180 phase maps based on the Hilbert transform (HT) of the APs (Warren et al., 2003; Yamazaki et al.,
 181 2012)(5) by computing the instantaneous phase θ (6), whose values ranged from $-\pi$ to π radians:

182

$$183 \quad \text{HT}[V(t)] = \frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{V(\tau)}{t - \tau} \cdot d\tau \quad (5)$$

184

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\text{HT}[V(t)]}{V(t)} \right) \quad (6)$$

185 where V is the membrane potential. Then PSs, where all phases converge (7), were computed to track
 186 the rotor trajectory:

187

188

$$\oint \nabla \theta \, dr = \pm 2\pi \quad (7)$$

189 PS detections were also used to assess heterogeneity degree in the tissue due to the inclusion of
 190 fibrotic regions.

191 **2.6 Implementation**

192 The differential equations of the cellular models were solved using the Rush-Larsen method for the
 193 gating variables and the forward Euler method for all other ordinary differential equations with a time
 194 step of $10 \mu\text{s}$. The monodomain equation (4) was solved using the finite elements method with “no

195 flux” boundary condition.

196 Simulations were implemented in C++ and CUDA languages. Computations were performed on an
 197 Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2603v3 processor with an NVIDIA Tesla K40c graphic card (see Figure
 198 S2).

199 3 Results

200 3.1 Cellular simulations

201 Figure 1 shows the APs obtained in cellular simulations with a BCL of 1000 ms under normal sinus
 202 rhythm (Panel A) and PeAF (Panel B) conditions, highlighting the differences in APD₉₀ for each atrial
 203 region. Under physiological conditions, the APD₉₀ was 236.4 ms for RA, 214 ms for LA, 176.1 ms for
 204 PV, and 292.8 ms for CT. However, under PeAF conditions APD₉₀ was 165.5 ms, 139.8 ms, 120.8 ms,
 205 and 180.2 ms for the RA, LA, PV, and CT, respectively. APD₉₀ decreased by 40% for RA, LA, and
 206 CT and by approximately 30% for PV with respect to normal conditions (see Panel C). In PaAF, in
 207 addition to APD shortening, RMP dropped from -75 mV to -79 mV and dV/dt_{max} increased from 163
 208 V/s to 168 V/s for RA, CT, and LA. RMP fell from -68 mV to -78 mV and dV/dt_{max} rose from 157 V/s
 209 to 165 V/s for PV (see Panels E and D).

210 When fibroblasts were coupled to a single myocyte, we analyzed the effect of their electrophysiological
 211 characteristics (RMP_f and C_{mf}) on myocyte electrical behavior (see Figure 2). When the number of
 212 coupled fibroblasts increased, the myocyte RMP became more depolarized and moved closer to the
 213 value of RMP_f. A higher C_{mf} value seemed to further reduce myocyte APD when RMP_f was -45 mV.

214 Figure 3 shows the effect of myocyte fibroblast coupling at different BCLs. As can be seen in Panel A,
 215 at a BCL of 300 ms myocyte AP was barely affected by coupling 1 fibroblast. APD₉₀ was very slightly
 216 reduced at both RMP_f values (purple and green traces in panel A), for all BCLs.

217 In panel B at higher C_{mf} the effect on APD_{90s} was similar to Panel A, except for the fact that an RMP_f
 218 of -26 mV, APD₉₀ was slightly higher than for an RMP_f of -45 mV, for all BCLs. As the number of
 219 fibroblasts increased (Panels C, D, E, and F), the effects changed with the electrical characteristics of
 220 the fibroblasts and the BCL. Panels C and D show that for a different RMP_f, APD₉₀ changed with BCL.
 221 Longer APD_{90s} were obtained for BCLs of 500 ms and 1000 ms for a RMP_f of -26 mV. In Panel D,
 222 for a BCL of 300 ms, APD alternans arose, and APD₉₀ increased with higher BCL at an RMP_f of -26
 223 mV. When the number of coupled fibroblasts increased (Panels E and F), APD₉₀ was reduced to 50
 224 ms for -45 mV and all BCLs and to less than 40 ms for an RMP_f of -26 mV.

225 We also analyzed myocyte RMP and dV/dt_{max} (see Figure 4). Myocyte RMP (Panel B) changed
 226 similarly when C_{mf} increased for both RMP_f values (-26 mV and -45 mV). Increasing the number of
 227 fibroblasts moved the myocyte RMP closer to RMP_f. The most significant change was in the dV/dt_{max}
 228 (Panel A), which was much lower at an RMP_f of -26 mV than the reduction obtained at an RMP_f of -
 229 45 mV. When fibroblasts couple to myocytes their RMP_f move closer to each other and more Na⁺
 230 channels are available, although myocyte Na⁺ channel availability can be reduced due to a more
 231 depolarized RMP according to the number of coupled fibroblasts.

232 The experimental data agree with previous simulation studies in which fibroblasts presented an RMP
 233 of around -45 mV and a C_{mf} of 6.3 pF, while myofibroblasts have a more depolarized RMP_f of -26 mV
 234 and a C_{mf} of 50.4 pF (Sridhar et al., 2017). In all the different atrial zones we analyzed the effects of
 235 coupling 3 fibroblasts or 3 myofibroblasts to a single myocyte (see Figure 5).

236 Panel A in Figure 5 shows how APD₉₀ was reduced when fibroblasts were coupled for all BCLs. When
 237 myofibroblasts were coupled, for a BCL of 300 ms APD alternans arose and for a BCL of 1000 ms

238 APD₉₀ increased. Panel B shows APD_{90s} in LA for different BCLs and similar fibroblast and
239 myofibroblasts effects. The reduced APD₉₀ in the PV case (Panel C) seems to be more pronounced in
240 myofibroblast coupling. CT alternans also arose when myofibroblasts were coupled.

241 3.2 1D strand simulations

242 Conduction velocity in the atria changes locally according to the region's characteristics, as shown in
243 Figure 6. During nSR and without fibroblasts, the RA has a CV of 70 cm/s, CT has a CV of 100 cm/s,
244 LA has a CV of 70 cm/s, and PV has a CV of 80 cm/s (blue discontinuous lines) (Ferrer et al., 2015).
245 Action potential propagation along the strand was affected by PeAF electrical remodeling (red
246 discontinuous lines) and CVs dropped significantly. At higher fibroblast (yellow) or myofibroblasts
247 (green) densities in the strand, CV dropped. Boxplot measurements of the CV are represented for the
248 100 random distributions of fibroblasts for each density (10%, 20%, and 40%). The region with the
249 greatest differential effect on CV was the PV, depending on whether the distribution was with
250 fibroblasts or myofibroblasts. PV also experienced conduction blocks in some of the random
251 distributions (indicated by yellow asterisks). Conduction block was also seen in LA at a density of 40%
252 in some distributions.

253 3.3 2D tissue simulations

254 The 2D atrial tissue electrical activity in PeAF with different myofibroblast densities was analyzed to
255 assess vulnerability to reentry. Figure 7 shows snapshots of phase maps (taken at the same time). Re-
256 entrant circuits can be seen in the RA (top panels) and in the LA (bottom panels) in PeAF remodeling
257 and increasing levels of myofibroblast density from left to right (membrane potential snapshots can be
258 seen in Figure S4 in the supplementary material). In the absence of myofibroblasts a functional reentry
259 was obtained in RA and LA. The tip of these rotors (Figure 7, first column), corresponding to the PS
260 superimposed in white on the phase maps, describes a regular circular path, which agrees with the
261 results obtained in previous simulation studies (Wilhelms et al., 2013). In LA, the rotor tip describes a
262 smaller path due to the shorter wavelength caused by shorter LA ERP (Fernandez-Lozano et al., 2006;
263 Ferrer et al., 2015; Krueger et al., 2012).

264 When myofibroblasts were present in the center of the tissue (see Methods), the obstacle altered the
265 reentrant activity. Small percentages of myofibroblasts (10%-20%) allowed the wavefront to propagate
266 through the fibrotic region, but the electrophysiological heterogeneities of myofibroblasts and
267 myocytes caused wavebreaks, which were detected as PSs (quantified in Table S3 in the supplementary
268 material). However, propagation in the fibrotic region was practically blocked when myofibroblast
269 density was raised to 40%, which produced an anatomical reentry surrounding the fibrotic obstacle.
270 Since the wavefront did not propagate through the fibrotic region the number of wavebreaks was
271 significantly reduced, as were the number of PSs detected (see Table S3 in the supplementary material).

272 The myofibroblasts in the tissue increased reentry vulnerability, measured as the vulnerable window
273 (VW), a time interval for which premature S2 stimulation generates a reentry (Figure 8). In the RA the
274 vulnerable window in the absence of myofibroblasts was 37 ms. When myofibroblasts density was
275 raised to 10%, the VW increased to 38±0.0 ms. VW also increased (39±0.63 ms) when density was
276 raised to 20%, but at 40% VW dropped below the control value (35±0.82 ms). Interestingly, LA was
277 more sensitive to myofibroblasts with a larger VW than the RA. The LA VW in the absence of
278 myofibroblasts was 40 ms. When myofibroblast density was raised to 10%, VW rose to 40±0.0 ms, at
279 20% it increased to 40.5±0.53 ms and at 40% it dropped to 38±0.88 ms.

280 4 Discussion

281 Computational modeling was used to investigate the effect of coupling fibroblasts and myofibroblasts
282 to myocytes in four different regions of the atria during persistent atrial fibrillation. The study's major
283 findings can be summarized as follows: i) myocyte-fibroblast coupling heterogeneously shortens
284 myocyte APD and depolarizes the myocyte resting membrane potential in the 4 different atrial regions
285 These effects strongly depend on the fibroblast electrophysiology. ii) Fibroblasts, and specially
286 myofibroblasts, introduce heterogeneities in the atrial substrate which alter the propagation of the
287 action potential, slowing conduction velocity. iii) Fibroblasts-myofibroblasts change the atrial
288 substrate during PeAF, which alters the vulnerability to re-entries and the vulnerable window presents
289 a biphasic behavior related to myofibroblast density. These results suggest that the heterogeneity of the
290 atrial tissue in the presence of fibroblasts/myofibroblasts promotes reentrant events and alters the
291 dynamics of arrhythmogenic propagation.

292 **4.1 Heterogeneous effects of PeAF remodeling and electrical coupling of fibroblasts in atrial** 293 **tissues**

294 Atrial substrate is differently affected by PeAF remodeling and by the presence of fibroblasts, due to
295 the electrophysiological heterogeneity of the different atrial regions. Our results from isolated single
296 cells show differences in the RMP, dV/dt_{max} , and APD for the four different atrial regions (RA, LA,
297 CT, and PV) in nSR and in PeAF. These differences are in agreement with the simulations carried out
298 by Krueger et al. (2013), who reported the differential effects of AF remodeling in the different atrial
299 regions. It has to be noted that in contrast to the Krueger study, our model presents a long-term stability
300 in all regions in single-cell and tissue simulations and also considers the effect of fibroblast coupling.
301 To our knowledge, this is the first simulation study including the three components (atrial
302 heterogeneity, AF remodeling, and fibroblasts) using a detailed electrophysiological AP model for
303 fibroblasts and focusing on the analysis of the different effects exerted by fibrosis in the different atrial
304 regions. A recent study by Roney et al. (2018) showed that high PS density in the PVs favored the
305 effectiveness of PV isolation in ablation procedure. Their model also considered electrophysiological
306 remodeling in AF, electrophysiological heterogeneities in different atrial regions, and fibrosis was
307 simulated by changes in tissue conductivity. In a previous study (Roney et al., 2016), the same group
308 modeled fibrosis by different methods and did not consider either electrophysiological heterogeneities
309 in the atrial regions or AF remodeling to determine how different fibrosis models could affect rotor
310 dynamics.

311 Different experimental studies show that atrial fibroblasts have a different electrophysiology from
312 ventricular fibroblasts (Burstein and Nattel, 2008; MacCannell et al., 2007; Poulet et al., 2016;
313 Salvarani et al., 2017). Morgan et al. (2016) found that fibroblast electrophysiology changes the
314 dynamics of an arrhythmic process and provides relevant information on the effect of myocyte-
315 fibroblast coupling in the atria. Our results indicate that RMP_f, C_{mf} , and the number of coupled
316 fibroblasts altered the behavior of myocytes action potential, as was found in previous simulation
317 studies (Koivumäki et al., 2014a; Maleckar et al., 2009; Sridhar et al., 2017). Furthermore, in the
318 present study we found that introducing I_{Na} current into the fibroblast model had an interesting effect;
319 due to the high RMP of isolated fibroblasts I_{Na} current was blocked but when fibroblasts were coupled
320 with myocytes I_{Na} channels became available. Additionally, myocyte-fibroblast coupling led to a
321 partial inactivation of the myocyte I_{Na} due to the higher RMP in the myocyte.

322 Fibroblast electrophysiology (RMP_f and C_{mf}) changes myocyte AP characteristics (Jacquemet and
323 Henriquez, 2008, 2009; Maleckar et al., 2009). Our simulation results also show that electrical coupling
324 with myocytes increases atrial electrophysiological heterogeneity. Changes in the BCL altered the
325 behavior of the coupled cells, with different responses in different regions. Interestingly, myofibroblast
326 -myocyte coupling in regions with higher I_{K1} and I_{CaL} (RA and CT) exhibited more sensitivity to

327 changes in frequency, while regions with smaller I_{K1} and I_{CaL} (PV) developed no AP for any of the
328 BCLs. In contrast to McDowell et al. (2013), we defined different electric characteristics for the atrial
329 myofibroblasts, which have a different effect on myocyte action potential. Myofibroblasts act as the
330 current source, raising the myocyte RMP (Jacquemet and Henriquez, 2007) according to the number
331 of coupled myofibroblasts (Koivumäki et al., 2014a; Maleckar et al., 2009), thus leading to a partial
332 inactivation of the myocyte I_{Na} current (see Figure S5 in the supplementary material).

333 4.2 Heterogenous effects of fibrosis during PeAF in atrial tissues

334 Structural remodeling of the cardiac tissue contributes to reducing conduction velocity, delaying
335 regional functional activations, and increasing structural heterogeneities, which are important factors
336 for establishing a re-entrant driver or conduction block (Camelliti et al., 2005). Our results show that
337 fibroblasts and myofibroblasts can alter the activation time in a 1D tissue strand, in agreement with
338 different studies (Sachse et al., 2008; Xie et al., 2009). We implemented one hundred random
339 configurations for different fibroblast/myofibroblast densities in the four atrial regions. Zhan et al.
340 (2014) showed that fibroblasts can alter the CV and can lead to blocks in conduction with fibrosis
341 densities of 40% and 45%, our results showed that a high density (40%) led to conduction blocks in
342 the LA and that the PV was the most sensitive region to the presence of fibroblasts-myofibroblasts.
343 Similarly, in an experimental study Miragoli et al. (2006) showed that myofibroblast proliferation
344 changed the tissue conduction velocity and myocyte dV/dt_{max} . Our results showed a reduction in CV,
345 in agreement with several other experimental and simulation studies that found that fibroblasts-
346 myofibroblasts can establish an electric coupling with myocytes, reducing their dV/dt_{max} and activation
347 time, reflected in reduced CV (Miragoli et al., 2006; Rohr, 2009; Xie et al., 2009; Yue et al., 2011).
348 We also found a monotonic reduction in all four atrial regions.

349 Tanaka et al. (2007) have shown that local fibrosis distribution reduces CV in the different atrial
350 regions, in agreement with our results, which showed a reduced CV with a tendency to homogenize in
351 all four atrial regions. CV heterogeneity is responsible for giving the atria the characteristic activation
352 times (Nguyen et al., 2012); if all the regions were to have a homogenous CV, this might induce the
353 appropriate conditions for reentrant rhythms and conduction blocks (Gaspo et al., 1997). As the fast
354 conduction systems' (CT) conduction velocity was significantly reduced, this may be an interesting
355 mechanism for AF in the right atrium.

356 4.3 Vulnerability to reentry during PeAF in fibrotic tissue

357 Structural remodeling and endo-epicardial dissociation alter the atrial substrate and could produce
358 macroreentries and focal activity (Everett and Olgin, 2007; Verheule et al., 2014). When we analyzed
359 the propagation in different regions of the atria and at different myofibroblast densities, we found that
360 a low myofibroblasts percentage increased the number of PSs due to the wavebreaks. However, at
361 higher percentages, propagation through the fibrotic zone was blocked, the number of wavebreaks and
362 PSs decreased, and an anatomical reentry was anchored around the fibrotic zone, in agreement with
363 previous studies (McDowell et al., 2013; Roney et al., 2016). Several simulation studies have also
364 shown that reentry dynamics is altered by heterogeneities of the action potential in the cardiac tissue
365 (Colman et al., 2014; Varela et al., 2016), the presence of fibroblasts (Ashihara et al., 2012; Gomez et
366 al., 2014a; Morgan et al., 2016), and that PSs increase in the zones with fibroblasts (Saha et al., 2018).

367 Waks et al. (2014) demonstrated that the rotation dynamics depends on the atrial tissue (RA or LA)
368 and its electrophysiological characteristics, as did we in the present study, in which vulnerability to
369 reentries and the dynamics of the rotation depended on the atrial region. LA presented slightly higher
370 VWs, due to its shorter APD.

371 Gomez et al. (2014b) showed that the density of fibroblasts had a biphasic impact on the ventricular
372 vulnerable window for reentry, while our results showed the same VW biphasic behavior for the first
373 time in atrial tissue. Krul et al. (2015) found that local fibrosis is associated with reentrant activity,
374 comparable to our results at low fibroblast density (10%), which can be considered as a region of local
375 diffuse fibrosis, presented higher tissue vulnerability and resulted in multiple wavebreaks. When
376 myofibroblast density was raised (20%), tissue vulnerability to reentry rose and conduction blocks
377 occurred. However, at higher densities (40%) the conduction blocks also occurred but VW dropped,
378 as was found by Campos et al. (2018). This suggests that myocyte-fibroblast coupling in PeAF plays
379 an important role in AF (Morgan et al., 2014), with different effects in different atrial regions.

380 **5 Limitations**

381 Several limitations must be considered when drawing conclusions from the present study. Firstly, we
382 did not consider the effect of electrical remodeling due to cytokines like TGF-B, which have been
383 reported during structural remodeling and are known to affect myocyte action potential (Burstein and
384 Nattel, 2008; Nattel et al., 2008; Zahid et al., 2016a).

385 Secondly, as fibroblast electrophysiology and differentiation into myofibroblasts still remain unclear,
386 the models we used should be considered as an approximation (Nattel, 2018). Myofibroblast
387 electrophysiological characteristics are still not well understood. Furthermore, it is important to
388 highlight that although animal models and in vitro experiments prove the existence of electrotonic
389 coupling between myocytes and fibroblasts (Grand et al., 2014; Kohl et al., 2005; Miragoli et al., 2006;
390 Salvarani et al., 2017), this has not been reported in humans in vivo. However, human cardiac tissue
391 with fibrosis presents altered electrical behavior (Fukumoto et al., 2016; Krul et al., 2015).

392 Thirdly, the pulmonary vein AP model was built on the basis of the reported experimental data for
393 dogs and sheep APD₉₀ and RMP. Electrophysiological data from human isolated myocytes from PV
394 are still unavailable (Ehrlich et al., 2003).

395 Fourthly, while AF mechanisms are still unclear, there are different pathways by which reentrant
396 drivers can be generated and maintained. Several studies have shown how non-myocyte cells like
397 fibroblasts, macrophages (Hulsmans et al., 2017) and adipocytes (De Coster et al., 2018) alter the atrial
398 substrate and promote arrhythmias. The effects of non-myocytes or endo-epicardial dissociation have
399 not been considered in the present study, although these are factors which might alter the reentry
400 dynamics and would be interesting to analyze in future studies (Verheule et al., 2014).

401 Fifthly, we are aware that fibrosis is a complex structure involving different actors such as collagen
402 deposition, inflammatory cytokines and proteins which may alter the myocyte electrophysiology.
403 There are different approaches to simulating the fibrotic regions such as non-conductive elements (Ten
404 Tusscher et al., 2004), the paracrine effect changing the myocyte ion channel conductance (Zahid et
405 al., 2016a) and coupling to elements with a static RMP (Majumder et al., 2011) and using ionic models
406 to describe the electrophysiology of fibroblasts (McDowell et al., 2013; Morgan et al., 2016; Saha et
407 al., 2018).

408 Finally, we did not include the effect of different sizes or locations of fibrotic regions in the tissue. The
409 fibrotic regions can in fact attract rotors (Roy et al., 2018), and future studies in this line would shed
410 light into the mechanisms of chaotic rhythms when fibroblasts proliferate. Additionally, 3D
411 simulations have shown how fibroblasts and non-conductive areas can modify the dynamics of the
412 reentry (McDowell et al., 2013; Morgan et al., 2014). Zahid et al. introduced the paracrine effect,
413 modifying myocyte electrophysiology in the fibrotic region in 3D simulations (Zahid et al., 2016b)
414 reducing the action potential duration and the conductivity of the fibrotic region. We are also aware
415 that 3D simulations include further structural details. The work by Ferrer et al. (2015), among others,

416 presents a highly detailed atrial model. However, these simulations have a high computational cost
417 while 2D simulations are computationally more efficient and provide a detailed insight into arrhythmia
418 dynamics. Despite these limitations, we consider that our simulations represent a realistic
419 heterogeneous PeAF remodeling (electrophysiological and structural) scenario in the different atrial
420 regions and contribute a great deal to the understanding of AF mechanisms.

421 **6 Conclusions**

422 The results of the present simulation study show that fibroblast electrophysiology alters myocyte action
423 potential characteristics and leads to slower conduction velocity in atrial tissues affected by PeAF.
424 These changes are heterogeneous within the different atrial regions.

425 Myocyte-fibroblast coupling creates a substrate in which the dynamics of arrhythmic reentries changes
426 with the fibroblast density. By increasing the density of fibroblasts, reentries evolve from functional to
427 anatomical around the obstacle formed by the fibrotic region. We also observed biphasic behavior of
428 tissue vulnerability to reentries. Low myofibroblast densities (10% and 20%) increase the vulnerability
429 to reentry, while a higher density (40%) reduces tissue vulnerability.

430 **7 Conflict of Interest**

431 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
432 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

433 **8 Author Contributions**

434 JS (first author), JS, and BT contributed to the conception and design of the study. JFG, LR, and LMM
435 contributed to the development of the model. Computational simulations were performed by JS (first
436 author) and the analysis/interpretation of the results was performed by JS (first author), JS, and BT.
437 All authors contributed to drafting the manuscript and all revised and approved the submitted version.

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710 **Table 1.** Ionic conductance modifications

<i>Channel conductance</i>	<i>RA</i>	<i>LA</i>	<i>PV</i>	<i>CT</i>
<i>g_{to}</i>	1.0	1.0	0.25	0.55
<i>g_{Kr}</i>	1.0	1.6	4.8	0.55
<i>g_{CaL}</i>	1.0	0.67	0.3	1.0
<i>g_{K1}</i>	1.0	1.0	0.7425	1.0
<i>g_{Ks}</i>	1.0	1.0	5.12	1.0

711 Relative values for each atrial region (right atrium -RA-, left atrium -LA-, pulmonary veins -PV- and
 712 crista terminalis -CT-) with respect to the maximum conductance of the potassium transient outward
 713 current (g_{to}), potassium rapid current (g_{Kr}), calcium L-type current (g_{CaL}) and potassium slow current
 714 (g_{Ks}) in the Koivumäki model (Koivumäki et al., 2011).

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717 **Table 2.** Atrial fibrillation electrical remodeling

<i>L_{cell}</i>	<i>g_{CaL}</i>	<i>g_{to}</i>	<i>g_{sus}</i>	<i>g_{K1}</i>	<i>K_{NaCa}</i>	<i>cpumps</i>	<i>PLB</i>	<i>SLN</i>	<i>phos</i>	<i>RyR</i>
1.1	0.41	0.38	0.62	1.62	1.5	0.84	1.18	0.6	2	2

718 Based on experimental observations/prior computational works (Koivumäki et al., 2014b), to account
 719 for persistent atrial fibrillation remodeling the ionic and cellular parameters modified were: cell length
 720 (L_{cell}), conductance of calcium L-type current (g_{CaL}), conductance of potassium transient outward
 721 current (g_{to}), conductance of potassium sustained current (g_{sus}), conductance of potassium inward
 722 rectifier (g_{K1}), maximum conductance of Na^+/Ca^{2+} exchanger (K_{NaCa}), conductance of sarcoplasmic
 723 reticulum Ca^{2+} ATPase (SERCA) pump (*cpumps*), phospholamban (PLB), sarcolipin (SLN), baseline
 724 phosphorylation (*phos*), and ryanodine receptors (RyR). The values indicate the factor by which the
 725 original values are multiplied.

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730 **Figure 1.** Myocyte action potentials from four different regions of the atria: right atria (RA), left atria
731 (LA), pulmonary vein (PV), and crista terminalis (CT). **A)** Myocyte action potentials under normal
732 sinus rhythm (nSR). **B)** Myocyte action potentials under the effect of electrical remodeling during
733 persistent atrial fibrillation (PeAF). **C)** Myocyte action potential duration (APD₉₀) under nSR and
734 PeAF. **D)** Myocyte action potential maximum upstroke velocity (dV/dt_{max}) under nSR and PeAF. **E)**
735 Myocyte action potential resting membrane potential (RMP) under nSR and PeAF.

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737 **Figure 2.** Effect of fibroblast and myocyte coupling under persistent atrial fibrillation (PeAF) electrical
738 remodeling in RA (baseline model). First and second rows show fibroblasts resting membrane potential
739 (RMPf) of -26 mV and -45 mV, respectively for a fibroblast membrane capacitance (C_{mf}) of 6.3 pF
740 (first column) and 50.4 pF (second column). The different traces are action potentials of isolated
741 myocytes under PeAF (blue), one myocyte under PeAF coupled to 1 fibroblast (1:1) (dashed orange),
742 one myocyte under PeAF coupled to 3 fibroblasts (1:3) (dotted yellow), and one myocyte under PeAF
743 coupled to 9 fibroblasts (1:9) (dotted-dashed purple).

744

745 **Figure 3.** Action potential durations of myocytes in normal sinus rhythm (nSR), under persistent atrial
746 fibrillation electrical remodeling (PeAF) and after being coupled to fibroblasts with a resting membrane
747 potential (RMPf) of -26 mV or -45 mV in RA (baseline model). In the first column the membrane
748 capacitance of fibroblasts is 6.3 pF and in the second column 50.4 pF. One myocyte was coupled to
749 one fibroblast (1:1) (first row), three fibroblasts (1:3) (second row) and 9 fibroblasts (1:9) (third row).

750

751 **Figure 4.** Fibroblasts coupling effect on myocyte electrophysiology. **A)** Myocyte maximum upstroke
752 velocity (dV/dt_{max}). **B)** Myocyte resting membrane potential (RMP). The levels for myocytes in normal
753 sinus rhythm (nSR) and persistent atrial fibrillation (PeAF) conditions are given in blue and red,
754 respectively. Discontinuous lines are myocytes in PeAF coupled to one fibroblast (1:1), 3 (1:3), or 9
755 (1:9).

756

757 **Figure 5.** Myocyte action potential duration (APD) of four different regions of the atria under persistent
758 atrial fibrillation electrical remodeling (PeAF) coupled to 3 fibroblasts (Fib) or myofibroblasts
759 (MyoFib) stimulated at different basic cycle lengths (BCLs). **A)** Right atria (RA) **B)** Left atria (LA) **C)**
760 Pulmonary vein (PV) **D)** Crista terminalis (CT).

761

762 **Figure 6.** Conduction velocity (CV) of a tissue strand in four different regions of the atria with random
763 fibroblasts (Fib) or myofibroblast (MyoFib) distribution and different fibroblast densities. For each
764 density 100 random configurations were simulated. CV measurements are represented in boxplots. **A)**
765 Right atria (RA). **B)** Pulmonary vein (PV) **C)** Left atria (LA) **D)** Crista terminalis (CT).

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767 **Figure 7.** Instantaneous phase maps and phase singularities (in white) for different densities of
768 myofibroblasts (non fibrotic, 10%, 20%, and 40%) in the right atria (RA) and left atria (LA) under
769 conditions of persistent AF remodeling.

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771 **Figure 8.** Vulnerable window to reentry in atrial tissue with different densities of myofibroblasts
772 indicated in percentage for the right atrial (RA) in blue and the left atrial (LA) in red subject to
773 persistent atrial fibrillation remodeling.